

GeoGebra Quick Start Guide

for Vectors, Matrices, and Geometric Transformations

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GeoGebra Quick Start Guide

This guide explains how to use GeoGebra to create and manipulate vectors, points, and simple geometric objects, and to explore geometric transformations defined by matrices.

You do not need prior experience with GeoGebra. The aim is to help you produce clear diagrams that support your mathematical reasoning and aid understanding.

Why GeoGebra?

GeoGebra is used because it allows straightforward graphing and manipulation of vectors in both two and three dimensions, within a single interface.

Which Version of GeoGebra to Use

You should use GeoGebra Classic (web or app).

- Web: <https://www.geogebra.org/classic>
- Desktop app: available from <https://www.geogebra.org/> or through the relevant app store.

This version is preferable as it shows the Algebra and Graphics View side-by-side, and it behaves consistently across devices and operating systems.

Setting the View

When GeoGebra opens, ensure the Algebra View and Graphics View are visible (as in the above screenshot).

If they are not, click \equiv (menu) \rightarrow View
 \rightarrow tick both options.

Entering Vectors

Vectors are entered using the Vector command, which creates a vector from the origin to a specified point.

Use the following format:

$u = \text{Vector}((x, y))$

Example

$u = \text{Vector}((1, 1))$
 $v = \text{Vector}((-2, 2))$

Press *Enter* after each line.

Each vector will:

- appear as an arrow from the origin in the Graphics View, and
- be listed in the Algebra View.

Adding and Subtracting Vectors

Once vectors are defined, they can be combined directly.

Example

```
u=Vector((1,1))
v=Vector((-2,2))
u+v
u-v
```

GeoGebra will automatically create new vectors.

You can also name them explicitly:

```
m=3u+v
```

This is particularly helpful when plotting several related vectors at once.

Labelling and Formatting Vectors

To make diagrams clear and readable, GeoGebra provides two levels of formatting controls.

Quick Formatting (Recommended)

When you click on a vector in the Graphics View, a small contextual options toolbar appears at the top of the screen.

From this toolbar, you can quickly:

- show or hide the label,
- change colour,
- adjust line thickness,
- apply basic style options.

Options

Full Formatting and Settings

For more detailed control:

- right-click the vector and select *Settings*, or
- click the settings (⚙) icon in the options toolbar.

The Settings panel allows you to:

- rename objects,
- precisely control label position,
- adjust appearance in more detail,
- apply consistent styling across multiple objects.

Moving Vectors

GeoGebra allows you to drag vectors directly in the Graphics View.

1. Select the *Move* tool (arrow/mouse icon).
2. Click and drag a vector.

When a vector is moved:

- the vector itself is repositioned, and
- any vectors defined in terms of that vector are updated automatically.

Example

If $w=u+v$, then:

- dragging u will also move w ,
- dragging v will also move w ,

Note that in this case, dragging w is not possible, since w is defined in terms of u and v , and its position is fully determined by u and v .

Adding Sliders

Sliders allow you to define variables whose values can be changed interactively.

To create a slider:

1. Type a variable name into the Input Bar (e.g. a) and press *Enter*, or
2. Select the Slider tool from the toolbar and click in the Graphics View.

GeoGebra will create a slider with default settings, which can be adjusted via the full formatting instructions given above.

Note that once sliders have been created, they can be used when defining vectors.

Example

```
a
b
u=Vector((a,b))
```

Adding Points

In many situations, it is useful to work with points, particularly when constructing polygons.

Method 1 (Typing)

$$A = (1, 1)$$

This creates a point labelled A at the coordinates (1,1).

Method 2 (Using the Mouse)

1. Select the *Point* tool from the toolbar.
2. Click in the Graphics View where the point should appear.

GeoGebra also allows several points to be created at once by entering a list of points using curly brackets/braces.

Example

$$L = \{(0, 0), (1, 0), (1, 1), (0, 1)\}$$

This creates a list labelled L containing the four points (0,0), (1,0), (1,1) and (0,1).

The points are hidden by default, but can be shown by selecting them in the Algebra View.

Creating Polygons

If you have already created points, you can then form a polygon using these points as its vertices.

Method 1 (Using the Polygon Tool)

1. Select the *Polygon* tool
2. Click the created points in order (e.g. A, B, C, D).
3. Click the first point again to close the polygon.

Polygon tool

Method 2 (Typing)

```
Polygon(A, B, C, D)
```

This creates a polygon with A, B, C, D as vertices (in that order).

Note that GeoGebra computes side lengths and areas automatically, which are shown in the Algebra View.

Scalar Multiplication

To multiply a vector by a scalar, we use standard mathematical notation.

Example

```
u=Vector((2, 1.7))  
2u  
(-1/3)u
```

You can also name the vectors explicitly:

```
v=5u
```

These operations allow you to explore how scaling affects both the length (magnitude) and direction of a vector.

Entering Matrices

To enter a matrix in GeoGebra, use curly brackets.

In particular, to enter the matrix

$$A = \begin{pmatrix} a & b \\ c & d \end{pmatrix},$$

we use the format:

$$A = \{\{a, b\}, \{c, d\}\}$$

Notice that each inner pair of brackets represents one row of the matrix.

Example

$$A = \{\{2, 0\}, \{0, 1\}\}$$

This creates a 2×2 matrix, which appears in the Algebra View.

Matrices can also be defined using parameters and sliders.

Example

$$\begin{array}{l} a \\ b \\ B = \{\{a, 0\}, \{0, b\}\} \end{array}$$

Applying Matrices

Once a matrix has been defined, it can be used to transform vectors, points, and polygons.

In GeoGebra, this is done by entering

```
ApplyMatrix(A,X)
```

where A is a matrix, and X is a vector, point, or geometric object (such as a polygon).

Matrix–Vector Multiplication

If A is a matrix and u is a vector, then

```
v=ApplyMatrix(A,u)
```

creates the transformed vector $v = Au$.

Note that you may equivalently enter

```
v=Au
```

which performs the same matrix–vector multiplication.

Example

```
u=Vector((1,3))  
A={{2,0},{0,1}}  
v=ApplyMatrix(A,u)
```

Note: The command `ApplyMatrix(A,X)` is intended for transforming objects with the same dimension (e.g. 2D to 2D, or 3D to 3D).

If A is rectangular (so the transformation defined by A changes dimension), `ApplyMatrix` cannot be used and instead we multiply directly using $v=Au$

Applying a Matrix to a Polygon

Matrices can also be applied to geometric objects such as polygons.

If a square has already been defined by entering

```
O=(0,0)
P=(1,0)
Q=(1,1)
R=(0,1)
Square=Polygon(O,P,Q,R)
```

then entering

```
ApplyMatrix(A, Square)
```

creates the transformed square under the transformation defined by A.

Switching to 3D Graphics View

GeoGebra supports both 2D and 3D visualisation. By default, GeoGebra opens in 2D mode. To work with vectors or objects in three dimensions, you need to enable the 3D Graphics View.

How to Enable 3D Mode

1. Click the \equiv (menu) icon in the top-right corner.
2. Select *View*.
3. Tick 3D Graphics.

The 3D Graphics View will open alongside the existing views. You can show or hide other views at any time by ticking or unticking them from the View menu.

Working in 3D

Once the 3D Graphics View is enabled, vectors can be entered using the format

$u = \text{Vector}((x, y, z))$

Example

$u = \text{Vector}((1, 2, 3))$
 $v = \text{Vector}((2, 3, 4))$

You can rotate the view by clicking and dragging with the mouse.

Zoom controls work the same way as in 2D.

In addition, when the 3D Graphics View is active, a contextual options toolbar appears when the view is selected. From this toolbar, you can enable automatic rotation, which can be useful for visualising the vectors in space.

Adding Planes in 3D

In three dimensions, GeoGebra allows you to define planes explicitly.

If u and v are vectors in \mathbb{R}^3 , you can create a plane by entering

$\text{Plane}((0, 0, 0), u, v)$

This creates the plane through the origin that contains both u and v .

Note that GeoGebra also supports other ways of defining planes (e.g. using points or lines).

Adding Shapes in 3D

GeoGebra allows you to add standard geometric shapes in three dimensions.

Adding a Sphere

```
Sphere((0,0,0),1)
```

This creates a sphere of radius 1 centred at the origin by entering

Adding a Cube

```
Cube((0,0,0),(1,0,0))
```

This creates a cube with one vertex at the origin and another at (1,0,0).

